

Salinization Modeling As an Impact of Irrigation System Modernization: From Surface to Drip Irrigation

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Salinization is one of the major soil threats all around the globe. It affects the soil suitability for agriculture production and the quality and quantity of the final yields. Among many factors, salinization is connected to irrigation system type and irrigation water quality. Due to the global water scarcity problem, modernization of irrigation systems is in need to increase water use efficiency. This study aims to model salinization formation in the Nile delta of Egypt and to simulate the effect of irrigation system conversion from surface to drip irrigation (modernization). Simile, a modeling software, has been used to build a dynamic salinization model and to run the simulation process. Simulation results showed that irrigation water salinity is a controlling factor of salt accumulation in soil especially in case of high mixing of drainage water and irrigation water. Results revealed also that converting to drip irrigation increased salinization to alarming levels, due to the great abatement of salts leaching which used to happen in the traditional surface irrigation process. This proposes that modernization is not always the right decision. The study demonstrated that simulation is an excellent tool to predict the impacts of changes in soil dynamics. Also, this study has illustrated the importance of modeling and simulation to planners and decision-makers.

Keywords: Salinization, Modeling, Irrigation System, Drip Irrigation